

PRESERVATION OF LIBRARY COLLECTIONS AS A DETERMINANT OF USE AMONG POLYTECHNICS STUDENTS IN EDO, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated the preservation of library collections as a determinant of use among polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The study population comprised, students in public polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria. Three (3) objectives guided this study, Purposive sampling techniques were used in the study and instrumentation for data collection was questionnaire. The findings of this study revealed that the level of usage of library collections was high, the level of preservation of library collections was high, and the lack of skilled staff, erratic power supply, and poor staff human relations are some of the challenges to the use of library collections among polytechnic students in Edo State, Nigeria. The study recommended that public polytechnics administrators should provide adequate infrastructures and that the National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should make a law that requires librarians to be registered with the Librarian Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) before employing them.

Keywords: Library collections, preservation, polytechnics, utilizations.

Introduction

The library plays a crucial role in shaping information professionals and equipping them with the necessary skills and knowledge to meet society's needs. Nigeria is a culturally diverse nation with a rich heritage. The library plays a prominent role in preserving and promoting the country's cultural heritage, serving as custodians of historical documents, manuscripts, and other valuable artifacts (Sharif & Balamurugan, (2020). A library is a repository of the wisdom of great thinkers of the past, present, and future. Thus, libraries have responsibilities to preserve, conserve, and restore library materials. The missions of libraries are preservation and access to information. The preservation and conservation of library heritage are very important as it could be related to social, economic, political, historical, legal, or religious and could be used for future purpose, library recognizes the importance of preserving and promoting the country's rich cultural heritage (Albright & Crow, 2021).

Librarians are trained to collect, organize, and preserve cultural materials, such as manuscripts, rare books, photographs, and audiovisual resources (Kumar, 2010). The preservation and conservation of library heritage are essential as it could be related to social, economic, political, historical, legal, or religious purposes and could be used for future purposes. In the preservation and conservation of library materials, the library preserve the documents by considering the long-term preservation of the items while still allowing the end user to easily access

the materials. However, all library collections experience damage from use and decay from aging, so there is a need for the preservation and conservation of information resources. It is the responsibility of the library head and management to draft a suitable policy to preserve or conserve rare or old materials in different ways.

Library education encourages librarians to collaborate with local schools, universities, government agencies, and non (Opele et al, 2020). People in various disciplines including students, researchers use library resources for their work. Some clients visited libraries to obtain materials for pleasure reading or for leisure activities. Busayo (2011) emphasized that the role of libraries cannot be overemphasized in the provision of the much-needed facilities for the development of good reading habits and interest, as it caters for different reading interests at various stages of intellectual development and for pleasurable reading. The library can also be regarded as an agent for educational and social change. Agbama (2014) posited that if you teach a child how to read, you have made him a king. Developing the right reading culture helps nations develop, and no nation can develop without its people's reading culture. Reading makes a man, and it helps to develop the mind, to be informed, thoughtful, and constructive.

However, this researcher's observation and preliminary investigation revealed that libraries in polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria, did not have adequate preservation plans for information resources, which might pose challenges to library users. Disasters are generally unexpected events that have destructive consequences for library collections. Therefore, it is vital for any library to take every possible precaution to prevent the occurrence of an unavoidable disaster. Adeniran (2011) revealed that academic libraries serve two complementary purposes: to support the polytechnic curriculum and to support research on the information needs of faculty and students, which must reflect the constantly changing needs of their users. Proper planning backed up with good information resources will help students to achieve this aim; this can be achieved in libraries. A library is not a luxury but a gap filling the necessities of life.

Statement of the problem

A library is one of the systems put in place by polytechnics management for students to support research, teaching, and learning. The availability of information resources and easy access to library collections in polytechnic libraries help such libraries to gain accreditation for the program during the accreditation exercise. However, one thing is to provide access to users, while another thing is for the users to use the information resources. A preliminary investigation by this researcher revealed that the low use of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria, may be attributed to the poor preservation of library collections and the low use of library resources, as evidenced by the low logging in daily statistics records in the libraries. An investigation by Ivwighrehweta and Eireyi-Fidelis (2022) on the use of library resources revealed that low library usage may have an effect on the academic performance of students as a whole. The study aimed to investigate the relationship between preservation and use of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria.

Objective of the study

The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. Determine the level of library collection use among polytechnics students in Edo state, Nigeria;
- ii. Ascertain the preservation level of library collections among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria;
- iii. Find out the challenges in using library collections among polytechnics students in Edo state, Nigeria.

Review of the Related Literature

Nigeria is a culturally diverse nation with a rich heritage. The role of libraries in preserving and promoting the country's cultural heritage is numerous. Libraries serve as custodians of historical documents, manuscripts, and

other valuable artifacts (Sharma & Balamurugan, 2020). Librarians are trained in library and information science, records management, archives, and other information professionals. They are equipped with the knowledge and skills to preserve these materials, ensure their long-term accessibility, and safeguard Nigeria's cultural identity (Slade et al, 2014).

There are no libraries that are exempted from devastation, which can occur as a result of natural or manmade disasters. In libraries, archives, and museums, there is a likelihood of fire as the collections or resources are mostly organic. Once a fire starts, it is difficult to save the materials that get a fire. Information resources not directly engulfed in flames can be scorched by dust and smoke. Heat emitted from fire causes bindings to shrink and warp and melts the plastic base materials. Water used for fighting fire can cause enormous damage. Fire, floods, high winds, cyclones, and earthquakes are also agents of library collections deterioration (Albright & Crow, 2021). These will cause documents to absorb water, swell, warp, and become extremely vulnerable to physical damage. Dyes and ink may bleed and book pages may stick together. Leather bindings warp and change shape. The effects of disasters on library collections are too obvious to comprehend.

The conservation and preservation of deteriorating information resources in libraries have become a global phenomenon to which libraries must aggressively respond if their mission of providing information to their patrons is to be met (Akande, 2009). Improper and faulty library staff actions may cause deterioration to library materials. Cheap and improper materials are often used for repair and maintenance. Wrong insecticides are used for fumigation, repair, restoration, and lamination work, which are usually performed by untrained personnel. All these conditions cause deterioration or worse, aggravate deterioration of library materials (Mahapatra & Wamukoya, 2019).

Every library should have a written disaster preparedness and response plan containing a description of emergency procedures, an emergency supplies list, a disaster response outline, conservation experts, a list of staff volunteers, a list of external contacts and names, addresses, and home and work telephone numbers of emergency personnel. Libraries should also be equipped with a fire and smoke detection system and an automatic fire extinguishing system. The use of a matchstick or open flame and smoking should be strictly prohibit inside the library. Inflammable materials and chemicals should not be stored in the stacks. The telephone number of the fire office should be visibly and clearly exhibited. The location of the emergency gate must be clearly indicated. The electrical defects and faults should be set right in time (Bochare, (1997).

Preservation is the task of minimizing or reducing the physical and chemical deterioration of documents. Conservation is the maintenance of documents in a usable condition through the treatment and repair of individual items to slow the decay process or restore them to a usable state. Conservation includes study, diagnosis, preventive care, examination, treatment, and documentation using any methods that may prove effective in keeping that property in as close to its original condition and for as long as possible. Conservation actions are carried out for a variety of reasons including esthetic choices, stabilization, needs for structural integrity or cultural requirements for intangible continuity.

Utilization the Library Collections

Bature (2011) posited that an effective reading environment exists in a society where there is an awareness of the benefits to be derived from reading books and utilization of other information resources in the library are made accessible to all. Awareness can only exist in a society where a high percentage of the population is literate and therefore possesses the ability to read and write. Another fundamental requirement for effective use of information resources in libraries is the availability of appropriate books and, other printed and non-printed

materials. Effective utilization of the library by polytechnic students to a great extent depends on the conduciveness and adequacy of the facilities of the entire library environment.

Folorunso and Njoku (2016) found that the characteristics of library environment included good library building, seating arrangement, and availability of library resources, library furniture, personnel, temperature within the library, lighting, décor of the library (interior designs), signage within and outside the library, an conducive and attractive, clean, free from noise, with durable and comfortable furniture, and good lightening for meaningful study. A polytechnic library where these facilities are inadequate could result in the low use of information resources by students, researchers, and the institute community.

Oluwatobi et al (2014) conducted research on the utilization of information resources in libraries and discovered that students and academic staff use library resources to a high extent for academic purposes. Utilization is the use of items for a particular purpose. However library utilization, refers to the extent of use of libraries by students, staff for learning and researchers, information utilization is the actual use of acquired information. People's expectations are high regarding searching for information, and they feel frustrated when their expectations are not met. Therefore, their information needs should be understood to provide corresponding services.

An evaluative study of information resources and services conducted by Bitagi and Garba (2014) revealed that factors such as inadequate funding of the libraries were found to be militating against the provision and utilization of information resources and services. Utilization of library resources is essential for the existence and survival of any academic library. The extent to which information resources are utilized in academic libraries is usually captured by the library statistics, which are compiled on a daily basis by the library staff. Therefore, it becomes pertinent that in order to scale the extent to which library resources are utilized, the library staff must be proactive in providing statistics of usage on daily basis. This will serve as encouragement or otherwise to the libraries sponsors (Ozioko, et al. 2014).

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study population comprised all the students in public polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria. A sample size of 600 students was considered, and a purposive sampling technique was used for the study. The questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. Out of the 600 questionnaires distributed, 423 were returned (705%). The criterion mean for the study was set at 2.00, indicating that any mean above 2.00 will be considered high and the mean below 2.00 will be considered low. Research questions 1 and 2 used a 4-point Likert scale, whereas research question 3 used a simple percentage

Data analysis and discussion

Table1: Level of library resource usage among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria

Level of Library Usage	VH	H	VL	L	Means
I borrow books from the library for my course work.	96	227	66	34	2.91
I regularly visit the polytechnic library for academic purposes.	222	91	64	46	2.85
I use the library more during examination periods than during regular academic sessions.	207	66	81	69	2.64
I prefer to use the resources of the over online alternatives.	77	207	72	69	2.69
I find the library environment conducive to studying and research.	218	87	69	49	2.81
Average mean					2.78

Criterion means **2.00**

Table: 1 shows that with an average mean of 2.78, which is greater than the criterion mean of 2.00, the level of usage of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria, is high.

Table 2: Preservation level of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria

Level of preservation	VH	H	VL	L	Means
Do limited preservation materials pose threats to library resource preservation?	161	119	80	63	2.39
Does your library lack the expertise to preserve library resources?	172	122	77	52	2.53
Do environmental factors pose threats to library resource preservation?	108	157	103	55	2.25
Does the physical condition of library materials affect their preservation?	139	91	157	36	2.06
Environmental monitoring is one strategy that could be used	169	123	71	60	1.81
Average mean					2.21

Criterion mean **2.00**

Table 2: shows that with an average mean of 2.21, which is greater than the criterion mean of 2.00, the, level of preservation of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria, is high.

Table 3: Challenges in using library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria

Challenges in the use of library resources	Agree		Disagree		Total	
	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%
Inadequate library resources	267	63	156	37	423	100.0
Poor human-staff relations	285	67	138	33	423	100.0
The library is not convenient	272	64	151	36	423	100.0
Lack of skilled staff	314	74	109	26	423	100.0
Erratic power supply	288	68	135	32	423	100.0

Table 3: Challenges to the use of library resources. The respondents agreed that 314 (78%), 288 (68%), and 285 (67%) employees had a lack of skilled staff, erratic power supply, and poor staff human relations. This implies that the lack of skilled staff, erratic power supply, and poor human relations among staff are some challenges to the use of library resources.

Discussion of the findings

The study findings are discussed in line with the study objectives.

The findings reveal that the level of usage of library collections is high. Opele et al. (2020) conducted an investigative study and found that library education encourages librarians to collaborate with local schools, polytechnics, universities, government agencies, and nonprofit organizations to address the educational and informational needs of the community.

The study findings clearly reveal that the level of preservation of library resources is high. Sharma and Balamurugan (2020) agreed that libraries serve as custodians of historical documents, manuscripts, and other valuable artifacts.

Findings on the challenges to the use of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State The finding corresponds with the study by Bitagi and Garba (2014), who revealed that factors such as inadequate funding/resources of the libraries were found to be militating against the provision and utilization of information resources and services.

Conclusion

This study investigated the preservation of library collections as a determinant of use among polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria. The study found that the level of usage of library resources among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria, was high, the level of preservation of library collections was high, and the lack of skilled staff, erratic power supply, and poor staff human relations are some of the challenges of library collection utilization among polytechnics students in Edo State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The polytechnic administrator should provide adequate infrastructures to increase the usage of library collections in Edo state, Nigeria.
2. Public polytechnics in Edo State, Nigeria, should employ professional archivists to help sustain the level of preservation of library collections in Edo State, Nigeria.

3. The National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) should make a law that librarians must be registered with the Librarian Registration Council of Nigeria (LRCN) before employing them.

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